

A large magnifying glass is centered over a satellite-style map of Europe. The map shows landmasses in dark blue and city lights in yellow and white. The magnifying glass has a black frame and a grey handle.

OpenWebSearch.EU
“Piloting a Cooperative Open Web Search
Infrastructure to Support Europe’s Digital
Sovereignty”

Deliverable D4.1
Search application prototypes
Version 1.0

Open Web Search

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Preliminaries

i. Project Info

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ii. Project Partners

Acronym	Partner
UNI PASSAU	University of Passau
BADW-LRZ	Leibniz Supercomputing Centre of the Bavarian Academy of Sciences and Humanities
RU	Radboud University
WEBIS	Leipzig University
TUGraz	Graz University of Technology
DLR	German Aerospace Center
IT4I@VSB	Technical University of Ostrava
CERN	Organisation européenne pour la recherche nucléaire
OSF	Open Search Foundation e.V.
A1	A1 Slovenia
CSC	Tieteen tietotekniikan keskus Oy (IT Center for Science)
NLNET	Stichting NLnet
BUW	Bauhaus-Universität Weimar (Associated Partner)
SUMA-EV	SuMa e.V. - Verein für freien Wissenszugang (Associated Partner)

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iv. Deliverable Summary

This document describes the deliverable D4.1 “Search Application Prototypes” of the OpenWebSearch.eu project funded by the EC under the GA 101070014 within the Horizon Europe Framework programme. It reports on initial developments of search applications in the context of tasks T4.1 and T4.2, including a science search application and a restaurant recommender. Both application make use of the index data and technical infrastructure developed in the work packages 1-3. These applications serve as demonstrators how the Open Web Index can be used for a wide range of different applications.

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vii. Executive Summary

This deliverable consists of and describes two search applications that are part of work package 4. The first search application is the Science Search Application, which is created as outcome of Task 4.1. The second search application is the Location-based Search Application as part of Task 4.2. In addition, the MOSAIC framework for supporting the creation of search applications is also part of this deliverable. These three software packages are described in this deliverable and persistent links are provided to snapshots of the software. At this stage, the development of these packages is in an intermediate state and will be continued in the following year. The final results will be reported in Deliverable D4.4.

The Modular Search Application based on Index Fractions (MOSAIC) is a framework that enables developers of search application to build their own search applications using web index slices created by the OpenWebSearch.eu infrastructure. MOSAIC can be used as an out-of-the-box search application or as an underlying technology to create more complex applications. It is a generic search application that makes index slices searchable that have been retrieved from the Open Web Index of the OpenWebSearch.eu project. Index slices are small or medium sized indices containing web documents related to a certain topic or for a particular purpose. These slices contain various metadata, such as geo-coordinates, topics, and genres of the web documents.

In order to develop a science search application as outlined in Task T4.1, a vertical search engine has been developed in the field of environmental science and earth observation. This engine connects three data sources, which are a scientific digital library in this research field, earth observation catalogues containing visual maps related to specific environmental topics, and MOSAIC that provides web information from the Open Web Index in the field of disaster management. In this way web information produced by the OpenWebSearch.eu infrastructure is connected with information repositories in the field of earth observation and environmental science. The user can enter a query as a natural language text, which is fed to a query analyzer that efficiently extracts three different attributes: geospatial, temporal expressions, and keywords. These attributes are then sent to the Retrieval Engine which searches and retrieves the top hits via three different indices structures. The Dashboard displays the top hits, designed to show different facets that fit different search purposes and, therefore, fit users with different expertise.

In order to develop a privacy-preserving location-based search application as outlined in Task T4.2, a restaurant recommender has been created that makes use of index data from the OWI. It delivers restaurant recommendations on the mobile phone based on personal preferences and past activities. The restaurant recommender is a privacy-preserving, user-centric recommendation system that helps users discover restaurants based on their personal preferences, contextual information (e.g., time of day, calendar events), and location. The project consists of three main components: an Android mobile app, a back-end server, and a web interface. All components work together to provide a seamless experience across platforms, while ensuring minimalistic and privacy-protected data sharing. In order to preserve privacy and user data, a model has been created and applied in this application. This model is described in detail in deliverable D4.3, Section 4.

1. Introduction

One of the key goals of the OpenWebSearch.eu (OWS) project is the creation of an Open Web Index (OWI) that enables the development of various types of applications using web data. Work package 4 aims to support the development of vertical search engines (search applications) that consume index data retrieved from the OWI. In contrast to general purpose and large-scale search engines, such as Google or Microsoft Bing, vertical search engines serve specific domains or purposes, which also provide opportunities to optimize search and retrieval strategies. The reason for providing support methods is grounded in another key goal of OWS, which is the building of an ecosystem of vertical search engines and other applications based on OWS.

The support of the development of vertical search applications is provided on different levels. First, technical support is provided by explaining how a search application can be created using the OWS technical infrastructure. This is done by providing a technical documentation and a prototype application called MOSAIC, which serves as a blueprint for other applications (see Section 2). Second, search applications are being developed in WP4 (Sections 3 and 4), in order to demonstrate the feasibility and usefulness of the search application concept and the OWS technical infrastructure.

This deliverable is also closely connected to the deliverable D4.3 that presents models for privacy, transparency and trust. These models are designed for the use of OWS search applications, in order to increase the user experience and meet user expectations. The trust and transparency model outlines how to foster trust of the user and is ready to be included and applied by any search applications. The privacy model describes how to maintain user data without violating data protection needs. This model is created along the development of the location-based search application.

The core of this deliverable consists of the development and piloting of the science search application and the location-based search applications, as well as the MOSAIC framework. The first version of these software packages have been completed and uploaded to Zenodo¹. The further development of these applications will be reported in the final deliverable D4.4.

2. MOSAIC

The Modular Search Application based on Index Fractions (MOSAIC) is a framework that enables developers of search application to build their own applications using index slices from the OWI. MOSAIC can be used as out-of-the-box search application or as a underlying technology to create more complex applications.

2.1 Motivation and background

The Modular Search Application Based on Index Fraction (MOSAIC) is a framework and generic search application that makes index partitions searchable. Index partitions are small or medium sized indices (up to app. 200 MB) containing web documents related to a certain topic or for a particular purposes. This partitions are being created using the OpenWebSearch.eu infrastructure and contain various metadata, such as geo-coordinates, topics, and genres of the web documents. MOSAIC is built upon the Prototype Search Application and provides an Application Programming Interface (API) to search index partitions and to filter the results according to the above mentioned metadata.

¹ <https://zenodo.org/>

2.2 System architecture

At its core, MOSAIC integrates multiple subsystems and components to facilitate efficient search and retrieval processes. The utilized OWI partitions, comprising CIFF and Parquet files, are managed by the inverted index of the Apache Lucene core search engine library and enriched with metadata stored in DuckDB through the Java JDBC API. While Lucene is utilized for initial searching and ranking, the metadata is used for filtering and preparing the search results. MOSAIC also includes a central plugin management component, which is crucial for incorporating various modules and optional components into the core application. This component is responsible for managing the integration of these modules. The plugin management is realized using Apache Maven modules, which provide a structured and efficient way to handle dependencies and module integration. Modules and components can be easily enabled or disabled through a configuration file. HTTP requests from the front-end or other services, including URL query strings and filter parameters, are processed through a REST API built on the Quarkus web framework. The system supports both JSON and XML responses, thereby complying with a proprietary format as well as the OpenSearch protocol. API endpoints handle different functionalities, most importantly searching in OWI partitions by sending a query and receiving results. Figure 1 illustrates the simplified technical system architecture of MOSAIC.

Figure 1: System architecture of MOSAIC

2.3 Features and characteristics

Key features and main characteristics of MOSAIC are summarised in the following list:

- Easy use of one or more OpenWebSearch.eu index partitions: Index partitions can be created and downloaded from the Open Web Index and then easily integrated in MOSAIC. The search, using a single query, can be performed in one or more indices at the same time. Currently, the retrieved web documents are ranked within the respective indices but not across multiple indices.
- Modular approach: Modules can be developed and added that filter search results according to features in the metadata and provide additional information to the search results.

- Different usage modes: MOSAIC can be configured to individual needs: (a) out-of-the box with an integrated web interface, (b) as a service with a REST API to be integrated with a search application, (c) own metadata modules can be added, and (d) the source code can be modified.
- Proprietary and Open Search protocol: The REST API offers search results in two formats, a proprietary protocol (expressed in JSON) and the Open Search protocol (XML).
- Geo-coordinates: MOSAIC allows to filter search results according to geo-coordinates of the locations contained in the content by using a bounding box. Furthermore, geospatial metadata can be optionally added to the search result by enabling the respective metadata module.
- Dynamic plain text management: For performance reasons, plain text in the metadata can be stripped, which decreases the size of the metadata database and increases the search speed. Text snippets can be loaded on demand if the plain text is not fully available in the database.
- Apache Lucene: MOSAIC is based on the free and open source search engine software library Lucene that takes care for basic search and ranking functionality. In addition, specific Lucene Analyzer or custom analyzer can be used.
- DuckDB: MOSAIC employs the open-source relational database management system DuckDB that handles the metadata of the web documents and enables filtering search results. Metadata that is stored in Parquet files is dynamically imported into tables using DuckDB when launching the application.
- Quarkus: In order to expose MOSAIC via a REST API, the web service framework Quarkus is used. Particularly relevant for developers, it also supports live reload after source code changes by using Quarkus in development mode.
- Other common features are available, such as pagination, basic caching and index information overview for retrieving characteristics about available index partitions such as number of indexed documents and a set of a languages of the index partition's documents.

2.4 Installation and software package

MOSAIC is publicly available in a GitLab repository, where also further description is available in the README file. A snapshot of the current version is also available on Zenodo.

- GitLab repository: <https://opencode.it4i.eu/openwebsearcheu-public/mosaic>
- Snapshot on Zenodo: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13790237>

The technical project setup for the MOSAIC framework involves organizing the core application and additional modules and components within the *search-service* directory. This directory is the central part of the framework as it encompasses the web framework and REST API as well as it incorporates various metadata modules and optional components. One or multiple OWI partitions are stored in the resources directory by default, with each partition named specifically. Additionally, the *scripts* folder includes several shell scripts and batch files for both Unix-like operating systems and Windows respectively: one for importing CIFF files into Lucene indices, one for compiling the MOSAIC back-end and importing any unimported CIFF indices, and one for starting the core application with various configuration options via a CLI. Essentially, to build and start MOSAIC, it is sufficient to first run the *build* script and then the *start* script which require JDK 17 or newer as well as Maven 3.8.4 or newer. For further information on installation and execution options, see the README file in the GitLab repository.

2.5 Demonstration and testing

The software and its applicability has been tested at two events.

In May 2024 a hackathon has been organised by the TU Graz team, where search applications were created with the help of MOSAIC. In total 12 computer science students organised in four groups developed several solutions in one day. All of them connected MOSAIC with LLMs, including solutions for query improvement and text summaries of the search results. The participant reported that MOSAIC was easy to use and integrate for an own application.

In August 2024 a workshop in the context of the exhibition “DigiDic – Call for Digital Self-Defence” was organised in Graz. The workshop lasted 2,5 hours where the participants without specific computer skills were instructed to create a personal search engine using MOSAIC. In total, 10 people participated the workshop. In a feedback discussion at the end of the workshop, the participants reported that they attained a good understanding of the overall concept. Difficulties could be observed in installing Java, Maven and Docker as prerequisite for MOSAIC.

2.6 Outlook and future work

Currently, MOSAIC is already usable as a simple search engine for index files downloaded from the OWI and as a basis for creating own search applications. Nevertheless future work will be applied to improve the software and to integrate generative AI features.

Potential features to improve the software include (a) the use of auxiliary Parquet files containing further metadata, (b) improving the overall process of installing the software, (c) improving the search ranking algorithm instead of using the default one from Lucene, and (d) creating a new front-end that can also be used by end-users.

An important update will include the integration of Gen AI and RAG (Retrieval-Augmented Generation) based features. For example, query improvement and search result summaries can be integrated into MOSAIC.

3. Science search application

The science search engine deliverable focuses on designing and building a vertical search engine for a specific scientific domain, earth observation, incorporating the transparency philosophy of Open Web Search for including and reusing open data. The methodology used is four-fold: a.) Design phase, where the conceptual design is defined; 2) Prototype phase, where the data sources and web application are developed; 3) the Evaluation phase, where experts and non-experts evaluate the application; 4) Reflection phase, where updates and future map is defined based on the evaluation. Overall, the conceptual design focuses on how the user input (query) is interpreted by extracting geolocation attributes along with keywords, and it focuses on how the data is retrieved from three different data architectures: i) Graph Database exploiting synergy between different text genres (e.g., publications, images), ii) science index using traditionally focused search index for a scientific domain, covering a wide range of text genres (e.g., blog posts), and iii) domain-specific source exploiting existing domain-specific technology to enrich the search engine results.

3.1 Motivation, background, and goals

Scientific research is marked by an overwhelming abundance of open data across various fields, challenging researchers to access and interlink relevant data. Existing work facilitates science search through specialized search applications, but they usually use one-genre science-related data (e.g., publications, research datasets, or open-source software), ignoring the considerable potential of relevant information available on the web nowadays consequently, restricting users from exploring and interlinking different scientific genres.

This work presents a conceptual design for a vertical search engine for the science domain that aligns with the Open Search Foundation (OSF) ideology. The architecture incorporates two main core components that differentiate it from other work. The query analyzer (Figure 2-yellow) provides categorized expressions such as keywords, location, and other criteria, directing the results more accurately, and a multi-structural search indices (Figure 2-blue) for rich contextual results.

Figure 2: A modular overview of the conceptual architecture of the vertical scientific search engine. It includes on the front-end side the **User Interface** (Green), where the user sends natural language queries and filters; then, on the Backend side (in Yellow), the **Query Analyzer** extracts the keywords and geolocation information from the query and sends it to the **Retrieval Engine** (RE). The RE retrieves ranked documents from three different datasources, curated for the scientific domain (in Blue): a.) a knowledge graph combining scientific articles and artifacts, b.) a search index containing scientific domain-specific URLs, and c.) domain-specific scientific artifacts.

Overall, Figure 2 illustrates the conceptual design, revealing three main components (from left to right):

1. The **User Interface**, as part of the front end, allows the user to search via a natural language query and other filters (e.g., Author's name). It allows the user to visualize the results in multiple views, whether as a list of ranked search results or a map view.
2. As part of the Backend, the **Query Analyzer** extracts keywords and other criteria (e.g., location, time), steering the results towards not only keyword- but also criteria-based focus such as Geolocation.
3. The keywords and criteria are sent to the **Retrieval Engine** that relies on different structures of search within a single search engine, each serving different capabilities, as illustrated in Figure 2-blue: a.) Knowledge Graph Search enables exploratory science search by interconnecting science articles and artifacts in one graphical database, b.) Web Search (a.k.a traditional search): enables access to a broad type of web-content (e.g., blogs, journals) with the ease of

expansion, and c.) specialized search enables access to curated domain-specific up-to-date data.

Based on our conceptual design, we developed a functional prototype for the earth observation and Earth Science domains, focusing on geospatial data (e.g., satellite imagery). It targets geoscientists, earth observation researchers, and people generally interested in geospatial data. The development phase included gathering data, building and integrating a multi-structural search, and developing a web application to visualize the data and facilitate user interaction.

To showcase the usability of our web application, we conducted a user study to evaluate the prototype by expert and non-expert users, revealing the usability of having multiple datasources, but improving the user interface would be needed to avoid overwhelming users with information.

Our contributions are summarized as follows:

- A new concept for a domain-specific vertical search engine using multi-structural index-based search.
- A search engine by curating domain-specific data and leveraging the OWS open index, removing the burden of index building and maintenance.
- A search engine prototype for earth observation domain with a user evaluation proving the importance of having multi-faceted data-sources in one search engine.
- An updated interface built upon the evaluation outcome (see Figure 6).

3.2 Overall concept and data sources

This section details the conceptual design for developing a Vertical Search Engine for a science domain. As mentioned earlier, Figure 2 displays the different modules of the application: After the user specifies the search parameters in the search user interface (Figure 2-green), the client initiates a search request to the Backend modules (Figure 2-yellow). The query analyzer module then extracts relevant information from the keyword query, such as time and location expressions, which results in an extended query. This extended query is then forwarded to the retrieval engine, which coordinates the retrieval of relevant content from multiple indices (Figure 2-blue) from multiple datasources (Figure 2-purple). After consolidating the responses, the retrieval engine forwards the final aggregated and ranked search results to the Search User Interface to render and visualize them in various interface components. In the following sections, we detail each module.

The core focus of architecture lies in two main components: query analyzer (e.g., topic, geospatial) and retrieval engine, which are explained below:

Query Analyzer

The main search query is a textual content search, in which the users can express their information needs with a simple keyword query in natural language. The text query is processed to extract specific information to steer the research with specific criteria (e.g., location expression). Because we focus on the *geospatial use case*, the query analyzer mainly takes as input textual data and extracts the following parameters:

- **Textual:** keyword query in natural language
- **Spatial:** geographic points and areas
- **Temporal:** time intervals
- **Topic / Theme:** domain-specific themes, topics, and keywords.

Multi-Structural Search Index

The approach emphasizes a multi-structural design of the search indices to encourage three goals, as depicted in Figure 3:

- 1) exploratory science via Knowledge Graph search (**Exploratory Science Search**),
- 2) broad domain search by building a search index from the web (**Web Search**), and
- 3) domain-specific data source for fetching specialized and up-to-date information (**Specialized Search**).

Figure 3: Intersection of the three Search types

As shown in Figure 3-Blue, our approach intersects science search, web search, and specialized search, combining information from various sources into a single user interface. Ultimately, the proposed vertical search application enable researchers to find synergy by interlinking different sources. We elaborate on each search type below:

Exploratory Science search. This search structure interconnects scientific publications (e.g., Journal or conference articles) with scientific artifacts, such as geospatial artifacts, open-source code, and datasets. The exploratory search is achieved by building a single knowledge graph (KG) connecting with an ontology containing both datatypes. More precisely, the web application focuses on Earth Observation domain. Therefore, the ontology of the KG, as shown in Figure 4, defines the existing entity classes and types of relationships between these entities. The ontology interconnects scientific publications with the Earth Observation field and domain-specific aspects (e.g., STAC¹ source, EO mission). The nodes of the KG are listed below

- **Publication:** represents a scientific publication.
- **STAC Source:** represents a STAC provider that provides EO data via a STAC API
- **STAC Collection:** represents a STAC Collection
- **Author:** represents a person who is listed as author of a scientific publication
- **EO Mission:** represents a satellite mission that provides EO data
- **EO Instruments:** represents a scientific measurement device which is on board of an EO satellite mission
- **Keyword:** represents a keyword, mainly in the context of scientific literature, concepts, and terms that are related to the specific use case

At the center of this knowledge graph are the publications and STAC collections. Both entity classes are connected with each other through the *Keyword* collection with the relationship *HasKeyword*.

Both Publications and STAC Collections are connected to EO Missions and EO Instruments with the relationship *Mentions*. Additionally, an EO Mission can contain multiple EO Instruments, which is represented in the edge relation *Is Equipped With*

Figure 4: Underlying Ontology of Knowledge Graph

Web Search refers to any information available on the web, including news articles, informative websites about topics and concepts (e.g., Wikipedia), social media posts, and discussions. Much scientific information, such as science blogs and scientific news articles, that address non-academic audiences is available on the web, which can widen the narrative for one scientific domain by maintaining the focus on the topics handled by this domain. To keep the information in this search structure relevant, only specialized search indices linked to the science domain are selected. To date a topic specific search index of 440 manually selected websites relevant to the earth observation domain is used for demonstration purposes. In the next iteration of the prototype larger shards of the OWS index will be incorporated using automatic filtering.

Specialized Search refers to specialized data linked to the science domain and developed by domain experts only. This data is usually external. For our *Earth Observation (EO)* use case, we focus on data for geographical locations, such as earth observation or environmental research data. This search type partially overlaps with science search since many relevant specialized data and scientific search are connected.

Integrating these three search types would lead to a more holistic and general approach to discovering and accessing scientific information and data sources.

3.3 User interface and Development

This section illustrates the user interface and the technical development of the earth observation Web Application.

Figure 5: Design sketch for the search user interface: The Input (on top) contains a search bar with a filter option. The Output (bottom) contains a dashboard with two toggled views: the document list, and map view. The titles (in green) are clickable and redirects the user to the selected item. The purple links (keywords, authors and properties) re-conduct the search to match the selected attribute and value.

The science search engine is a vertical search engine for a specific scientific domain, earth observation. The user enters a query as a natural language text, which is fed to a query analyzer that efficiently extracts three different attributes: geospatial, temporal expressions, and keywords. These attributes are then sent to the Retrieval Engine which searches and retrieves the top hits via three different indices structures.

- Explorative search: A graph database that links EO publications (from elib.de) to STAC² API items via keywords
- Specialized Search: STAC Items represent an EO-specialized dataset, which is fetched via API, saved, and then accessed via the search engine.
- Web Search: A traditional index (created via ChatNoir for this version) contained predefined web blogs and pages for EO.

The Dashboard, as illustrated in Figure 6, displays the top hits, designed to show different facets that fit different search purposes and, therefore, fit users with different expertise. In addition, the toggle elements (e.g., only one search genre appears at a time) avoid information overload. The Dashboard contains two main interface component views: a document list and an interactive map (Figure 6 and 7).

² STAC (Spatio Temporal Asset Catalogues) is a common standard to describe and access geospatial information across data providers in a unified way (see <https://stacspec.org/en>).

Figure 6: Illustration of the User Interface (version 1). This version was evaluated as described in Section 3.5

3.4 Software package and Installation

Currently, two versions of the search application are available. Both have been uploaded to Zenodo and contain a README file that provides instructions how to install and run the software.

The first version of web-application was developed using Vue and Flask (python) and is accessible:

- **Zenodo:** <https://zenodo.org/records/13788713>.
- **DOI:** <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13788713>

The second version of the web-application contains updates to the user interface, query suggestions and snippet summary generator (as explained below, under “Outlook and future plans” and illustrated in Figure 7):

- **Zenodo:** <https://zenodo.org/records/13789303>
- **DOI:** <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13789303>

Figure 7: Illustration of the updated User Interface (version 2). The usability, font colors and structure is improved.

3.5 Evaluation

An evaluation was done for the first version of the prototype, shown in Figure 6.

Objective

The evaluation had two broad objectives:

- Evaluating the conceptual design: integrating multiple heterogeneous data sources from different domains in a single search user interface, as well as integrating web search capabilities within a science search application
- Evaluating the usability of the prototype (see Version 1.0)

User Study and Participants

The evaluation consisted of a User Guide containing an overview of the web application, defined tasks, and a questionnaire capturing qualitative aspects of the participants' perceptions of the search user interface and the science search application in general.

The web application was available online, so participants could finish the user study independently. Each participant had to do two tasks:

- Task 1: Search for wildfire events and explore all the search hit genres in the Document list view: publications, webpages, satellite images, etc. This task evaluates the usability of different data sources for a specific search task to explore a single query (in this case, 'wildfire events').
- Task 2: Searching for "Land cover" focusing on the Map View, where the user formulates data requests for satellite imagery for a certain area and STAC Collection.

In total, 18 participants conducted the tasks and questionnaires, and they were from the German Aerospace Center and Graz University of Technology. Fifteen of them hold a university degree, and three have a High School degree. While the majority of participants (n=11) work or study in some field

of Computer Science, the remaining participants are distributed across fields such as earth observation, psychology, migration and urban areas, biochemistry, chemical engineering, biomedical engineering, and medicine.

Results and Takeaways

The outcome of the evaluation is as follows:

- Participants valued the multi-structural index results.
- Participants found the geospatial visualization of the metadata to be helpful.
- Participants found the Document and Map views to be helpful.
- Participants noted that some aspects can be improved, such as:
 - Tackling information overload due to the different result types
 - Improving the usability of the advanced search (adding more attributes to the search)
 - Enriching the metadata visualization by incorporating, for example, temporal data

3.6 Outlook and future plans

The current and future work focus on improving the existing components within the Frontend and Backend, and enhancing features with large language models. Details are listed below:

- Improving the User Interface (as shown in the previous section 3.3) to tackle the data overload issue and usability. Figure 6 and 7 illustrate the changes done.
- Improving the Query Analyzer to extract accurate temporal and spatial data.
- Replacing the *keyword* tagging with an improved version: The keywords will include an established earth observation taxonomy.
- Implementing a new *query recommender* and *optimizer* using Instruction-based LLM.
- Integrating conversational search using multi-modal earth observation data.

4. Location-based search application

The Restaurant Recommender project is a privacy-preserving, user-centric recommendation system that helps users discover restaurants based on their personal preferences, contextual information (e.g., time of day, calendar events), and location. The project consists of three main components: an Android mobile app, a backend server, and a web interface. All components work together to provide a seamless experience across platforms, while ensuring minimalistic and privacy-protected data sharing. Figure 8 outlines the system. OWS index is used for indexing data from various restaurant platforms such as TripAdvisor, Yelp, Zomato, and Open Table. The indexed data includes restaurant descriptions, images, user ratings, comments, types of meals, cultural classifications, food types, and suitability for various occasions. A Large Language Model (i.e. gtp 4o) is delivered to extract features from the semi-structured data and create the dataset which is used to develop a collaborative filtering-based recommender and the content-based filtering model. The collaborative filtering-based recommender infers the best restaurant choices based on user preferences and user-context, extracted from natural language query. While the content-based filtering recommender recommends restaurants that are similar to a given restaurant based on the attributes or features of the items. We uses item metadata similar to the one used in collaborative filtering-based recommender, such as cuisine, price, meals, features and other

attributes. To access the recommender we have also deployed a simple web application and a mobile app.

Figure 8. Functional overview of the System.

In order to create a privacy-preserving mode of personalized recommendations, we facilitate concept of Query Imputation. The details are outlined in more detail in deliverable D4.3, Section 4. As outlined in figure 8, users initially fill out a questionnaire to provide basic preferences and context (i.e. for a cold start). The app collects contextual information like user behavior (e.g. history of searches, restaurants visited, ratings within the app), calendar events, and location data, which is processed and stored locally on the user's device. This information is used to augment and complete the natural language query by inferring missing features or contextual information, ensuring that the recommendations are highly relevant to the user's (momentary) needs. Overall the delivered solution emphasizes user privacy by processing sensitive data locally on the user's device and utilizing secure multi-party computation

4.1. Motivation, Background, Goal, Purpose

With the growing number of restaurants and diverse cuisine options, finding personalized dining recommendations can be challenging. Users need a way to discover restaurants based on their preferences, previous interactions, and location, while ensuring their privacy is protected. Existing platforms often expose sensitive data or prioritize recommendations based on advertising or financial incentives, limiting the user's control. A privacy-preserving approach is crucial to provide relevant, unbiased suggestions without compromising user data. Many recommendation systems use user data for personalization but often at the cost of privacy, exposing sensitive information to third parties. Open Index, a decentralized and privacy-preserving system, offers a way to improve personalization by indexing data from multiple platforms while maintaining user privacy. Collaborative filtering, combined with user-item similarity, allows for accurate recommendations while keeping data secure. The goal is to build a personalized restaurant recommender app that provides users with relevant suggestions based on their search history, clicked restaurants, and location. The purpose is to enhance user satisfaction by offering tailored restaurant recommendations, increasing discoverability of nearby or favourite restaurants, and simplifying the decision-making process.

4.2. Overall Concept Software Architecture

Frontend (Kotlin-based Android Application):

- **Kotlin:** The app is developed using Kotlin, and the user interface is built with Jetpack Compose, which allows for declarative UI components and a reactive programming model.
- **Jetpack Compose UI:** The UI leverages composable functions to display restaurant information, search results, user preferences, and maps. Components like LazyColumn, Button, and TextField provide a smooth and flexible user interface experience.
- **User Preferences:** The app uses SharedPreferences to store data such as clicked restaurants, search history, and location, ensuring that sensitive information stays on the user's device in a privacy-preserving way.
- **Personalization:** Contextual information such as the user's location, time, and activity is collected, but never directly sent to the back-end or exposed directly to the AI model. Since the model operates on the concept of natural language queries this information is used to complement the natural language query. For instance, location is transformed into city, time is used to identify weather it is breakfast, lunch or dinner, restaurant visits are used to extract preferred types of cuisine, etc.

Backend:

- **API Server (Python):**
 - Handles requests for personalized recommendations.
 - Uses a restaurant database (CSV) with reviews and metadata.
 - Carries out inference over the search query generated in natural language.

Key Features:

- **Location-based recommendations:** Uses user's current location or selected city to provide nearby restaurant recommendations.
- **Similar search recommendations:** Allows users to search for restaurants based on the similarity with a specified restaurant name in the query.

Model (Figure 9):

The data to train the AI models, a subset of pages linked to TripAdvisor, is extracted from the Open Web Index. Since in the pilots we need to implement the recommendations for Slovenia, we chose TripAdvisor as it maintains the most complete and coherent data about restaurants. However, the approach is generalisable to any kind of content. From the *parquet* file we utilize the raw html data.

Figure 9. Overview of the weekly supervised flow of the recommendation system.

As outlined in Figure 9, the raw html data contained in the index, is passed to an LLM, at the moment we use GPT 4o model, to be structured and transformed into feature sets. With the feature sets we create a dataset, linking restaurant name and URI with the different features. In this way we achieve that a single restaurant can be described with multiple sets of features originating from multiple web-pages or sources. With the dataset we then train the two AI models: one for location-based feature search and another for similar restaurant search. The models are at the moment re-trained on weekly basis.

The Recommender Dataset

The dataset consists of detailed information about restaurants, including attributes related to their location, pricing, style, reviews, ratings, and working hours. Below is a description of the features:

- name: Name of the restaurant.
- city: The city where the restaurant is located.
- country: The country where the restaurant is located.
- price_range: The price category of the restaurant (e.g., mid-range, budget).
- style/cuisine: Describes the type of cuisine offered (e.g., vegetarian, European, Mediterranean).
- meals: Indicates the meals served (e.g., breakfast, lunch, dinner).
- features: Various features offered by the restaurant (e.g., Takeout, Reservations, Outdoor Seating, Wheelchair Accessible, Serves Alcohol, Free Wifi, Accepts Credit Cards, Live Music, etc.).
- reviews: Detailed customer reviews providing textual insights into the customer experience.
- ratings: A numerical rating (e.g., 4.0).
- working_hours: The restaurant's opening and closing hours.

We combine the restaurant features such as location, cuisine, price range, meals, and additional features into a single bag of words column, which consolidates the key attributes and processed reviews. Then, we apply TF-IDF (Term Frequency-Inverse Document Frequency) to measure the importance of these features and sort restaurant similarities based on how closely they match the user query from the frontend, allowing for more accurate recommendations.

A screenshot of the dataset is displayed in the picture below.

```

1 name,city,country,price,style,reviews,ratings,working_hours,number_of_reviews,reviews_processed,style_processed,bag_of_words
2 Gostilna Amadeus,ptuj,slovenia,mid-range,"vegetarian friendly, lunch, dinner, european, slovenian, central european","gostilna (aka inn, tavern
3 Operna Klet,ljubljana,slovenia,mid-range,"dinner, breakfast, lunch, seafood, mediterranean, slovenian, reservations, outdoor seating, seating,
4 Okrepcevalnica pri Mici,destrnik,slovenia,cheap-eats,"breakfast, lunch, dinner, pizza","hard to review: poor pizza good burger. i would say piz
5 Manjada...pu nase,izola,slovenia,mid-range,"vegetarian friendly, vegan options, gluten free options, lunch, dinner, italian, pizza, seafood, me
6 Asian Bistro OSHA,ljubljana,slovenia,cheap-eats,"vegetarian friendly, vegan options, breakfast, lunch, dinner, bar, street food, asian, thai, t
7 Soteska 8,ljubljana,slovenia,mid-range,"drinks, bar, cafe, pub, wine bar, outdoor seating, serves alcohol, wine and beer, accepts credit cards,
8 Restavracija&Lounge bar Svetilnik,izola,slovenia,mid-range,"vegetarian friendly, seafood, mediterranean, slovenian, pizza, european","fantastic
9 Atrium,ljubljana,slovenia,mid-range,"dinner, lunch, international, reservations, seating, table service","terrible service. i attempted to have
10 Sovdat,bovec,slovenia,mid-range,"vegetarian friendly, european, slovenian, central european, grill, offers table service, offers takeout, wheel
11 Nabrežje 15,ljubljana,slovenia,mid-range,"breakfast, dinner, drinks, italian, european, slovenian, reservations, outdoor seating, seating, tabl
12 CUBO Golf Restavracija,ljubljana,slovenia,"lunch, dinner, drinks, outdoor seating, parking available, highchairs available, wheelchair accessi
13 "Foodie, restavracija in kavarna",ljubljan,slovenia,mid-range,"italian, international, european, grill, slovenian",-1.0,0,italian internati
14 Pacug,portoroz,slovenia,"italian, european, grill, diner, slovenian",-1.0,0,italian european grill diner slovenian, slovenia portoroz itali

```

Figure 10. Screenshot of the dataset used to store information of the restaurants.

Collaborative Filtering Model for Location-based recommendations

In the Collaborative Filtering Model for Location-Based Recommendation, user feedback is first processed to extract important attributes such as the city, country, and price range. The system then filters the restaurant dataset accordingly, ensuring recommendations are aligned with the user's location and budget preferences. The input is then transformed using TF-IDF vectorization, matching the format of the restaurant data.

The next step involves computing Cosine Similarity between the TF-IDF vector of the user's input and the vectors of the filtered restaurants. This similarity score reflects how closely a restaurant's features match the user's description. The system ranks the restaurants based on these similarity scores and filters out entries with low relevance, providing the user with tailored restaurant recommendations that best match their preferences.

Content Filtering Model for Similar search recommendations

In the Content Filtering Model for Similar Search Recommendations, we leverage preprocessed restaurant data to suggest restaurants that are similar to a user-specified one. The model works by using Cosine Similarity to measure how closely related a given restaurant is to others based on various features like name, cuisine, and reviews.

The user inputs the name of a restaurant and the city they are in. The system first checks if the restaurant exists in the dataset. Once a match is found, the system retrieves a similarity score between the selected restaurant and others in the database. These similarity scores are calculated based on a precomputed similarity matrix that compares restaurants' features using the TF-IDF vectorization technique.

The system then returns a list of restaurants that have the highest similarity scores with the chosen restaurant. To ensure relevance, the system filters results to match the user's city and provides a sorted list of recommendations based on similarity scores, facilitating more personalized suggestions.

Query Imputation

Query Imputation is a technique used to enhance and expand a user's initial query to include relevant features that are important for the recommendation system but may not have been explicitly mentioned by the user.

(1) We begin with a simple query,

Italian restaurant for dinner tonight.

(2) The next step is to parse and identify missing features. We apply a combination of Natural Language Processing (NLP) techniques, including

- Tokenization, to break down the query into individual words or tokens.
- Part-of-Speech (POS) Tagging, to understand the grammatical structure of the query
- Keyword Extraction using TF-IDF to identify important keywords in the query that might correspond to features
- Named Entity Recognition (NER), for identifying specific entities in the query. In the case of our recommender we train them to classify text into the entities such as: Cuisine types, Location names, Price indicators (e.g., "cheap", "expensive"), Meal types (e.g., "dinner", "lunch"), Special features (e.g., "outdoor seating", "take-out"), Sitting type (e.g. “family friendly”, “pet-friendly”, “business-lunch”, etc.)
- Semantic Analysis: we use BERT embeddings to capture semantic meanings and identify words or phrases that are semantically similar to our feature set.
- Intent Classification: we train a classifier to categorize the overall intent of the query (e.g., finding a restaurant with specific features or finding a restaurant at location that similar to another restaurant).

(3) Next we try to extract missing features from the users contextual model (See D4.3 for more details on the model) stored on the device. We can use contextual information such as location, time of day, day of week, current events, user's popular choices and user's historical data and preferences to infer relevant features. The result of augmented Input query from step (1):

- Location: [User's current city]
- Cuisine: Italian
- Meal: Dinner
- Price Range: \$\$-\$\$\$ (based on user's typical choices)
- Features: Reservations available, Outdoor Seating (user's popular choices for dinner)
- Keywords: "authentic", "romantic" (common for Italian dinner choices)
- Sentiment: Positive reviews for dinner service

4.3. Usage

- **Open the app:** Users can search for restaurants by entering a natural language query in the search box, which contains the preferences for a restaurant, for example: “cheap Mexican food for lunch in Ljubljana”.

Figure 11. Interface of the mobile app.

- **Interact with restaurants:** Users can click on restaurants to get more details or navigate to their location via Maps (Currently only Google Maps supported).

Figure 12. User recommendations retrieved on Location Based Search option.

- **Receive personalized recommendations:** Based on search history, location, and clicked restaurants, the app will suggest personalized restaurant recommendations over time.

Figure 13. User recommendations retrieved on Similar Restaurant Search option.

4.4 Installation and Software Packages

The source code of the application has been uploaded to Zenodo and contains instructions how to install and run the software. It can be retrieved under the following link:

- Snapshot on Zenodo: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13785140>

The software contains the following software components and libraries:

- **Frontend (Android App):**
 - **Android Studio:** The main development environment.
 - **Jetpack Compose:** For building the user interface.
 - **Retrofit:** For making API calls to the backend.
 - **Google Play Services (FusedLocationProviderClient):** For fetching user location.
 - **SharedPreferences:** For storing user preferences like search history and clicked restaurants.
- **Backend:**
 - **Flask (Python) :** For handling API requests.

- **Pandas**: For reading and manipulating the restaurant data stored in CSV files.
- **Cosine Similarity**: Used to calculate the similarity between search queries and restaurant reviews.

Created Software Packages:

- **APK files**: app-debug.apk, output-metadata.json
- **Bundle file**: app-debug.app

4.5 Outlook and future plans

For the future development we plan to:

- integrate fully the Query Imputation pipeline
- integrate rating feature and a feedback loop to improve the similarity measures and personalization of responses
- to extend and test different LLMs that can be used for feature extraction (i.e. Llama3, Claude 3 and Mistral (Nemo and Large)),
- extend the app to be multilingual, i.e. focus on creating datasets for local languages and deliver a language translation pipeline to fully support multilingual interfaces not only based on location but also users language
- integrate multi-source datasets with a semi automated pipeline
- experiment with Large Vision Language Models to generate additional (contextual) information about the restaurant and food, and retrain the models.

5. Conclusion and Outlook

This deliverable reports on the initial development of search application prototypes. An overview of the developed software packages and links to snapshots of the source code is provided in the following tables.

MOSAIC

Name	MOSAIC Search Engine Framework
DOI	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13790237

Related task	T4.1 Open Science Search
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Science Search Application

Name	OWS for Science WebApplication Prototype
DOI	First version: https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13788713 Second version: https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13789303
Related task	T4.1 Open Science Search

Location-based search application

Name	Restaurant Recommendation Application
DOI	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13785140
Related task	T4.2 Mobile privacy-preserving, personalized recommendation of geo-entities

The development is still ongoing and the further development will be reported in the final deliverable of this work package (D4.4). Individual plans for the further development are listed in the respective sections of the search applications. Overall at least two goals will be pursued. First, the integration and connection of the applications with the index data retrieved from the OWI will be tightened. This includes the use of metadata added to the index files and the selection of the index partition by new filtering mechanisms. Second, new developments in the field of Generative AI and LLMs will be taken up the further research and development. For example search query can be improved to achieve better results or the the search result can be summarised.

Appendix

See included the list of Acronyms and Abbreviations used in OWS context.

Acronym / Abbreviation	Term
AI	Artificial Intelligence
LLM	Large Language Model
OSSYM	Open Search Symposium
OWI	Open Web Index

OWS or OWS.eu	OpenWebSearch.eu project
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